
THE SPECIAL FEATURE AND UNIQUENESS OF THE LANGUAGE AND STYLE OF TOGHAY MURAD’S WORKS

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Abstract: In this article, the language and style of the works of the national writer of Uzbekistan, Toghay Murad, his skill of using words, the skill of using words **especially** his skill in using words is not like other writers. the skill of using words specific to the unique Surkhan dialect is expressed.

Key words: Language, style, vocabulary, dialect, dialect.

Every writer and creator is completely different from each other with his own use of words and style, this is the same aspect that poets and writers follow each other in most cases, and in most cases they do not have any relation to each other. They try to find an original style, our famous writer Togay Murad also had such a unique style.

The stylistic difference of Togay Murad is that he introduced the speech of ordinary people of the Surkhan oasis, which was ignored by other artists, into the literary process for the first time as a style. Based on the opinion of the creators before him, he expressed his thoughts about the style. Researcher M. Khidirova also gives valuable information about this. Language is the basis of the work describes: An example of a work of art is a tower. The foundation of the work will be. The life of the work is built from this foundation. The foundation of the work - language Life begins with language, life ends with language. To this end, He says, "The tongue has come out" of the person who will come to life. Leaving life he says that a person is "left out of the tongue". This folk phrase is the life of the language and that it is a spiritual need is a wise one typical of Toghay Murad can be said to be an interpretation. Toghay Murad is unique like great teachers creativity, language style and word art are artistic skills for young writers serves as a school. Especially our mother tongue as the state language. It is great that we are all responsible for life and its development The creativity of our writers and artistic language lessons are more important earns. Art of Togay Murad's creative-aesthetic concept to study the expression of the writer's worldview and stylistic uniqueness is one of the main ways of understanding.

In scientific and literary sources, a series of definitions about the style of poets and writers in studies we will witness that it was given. For example, one of the great scholars is Abdurauf Fitrat is important in the formation of creative style and its artistic creation emphasizes the importance of the poet, among other things: "the

poet-writer begins to create a special style for himself as he rises in his artistic career. When the forms of the poet's imagination, thought, and understanding become complete and perfect, a suitable style will emerge.” It is not for nothing that the basic conditions of the artist’s style are mentioned in this definition. Or the great literary critic O. Sharafiddinov also interprets the originality of the creative style and it is a comprehensive concept as follows: “Innovation, original style is born as a result of long research and continuous work. Style is like the air we breathe every day - we breathe it without even thinking about breaking it down into its components. The style is embedded in the entire work of the writer. It can be called the spirit of creativity, the fragrance that can be found in every work. The peculiarities of the writer’s attitude to life, character creation, visual means, way of thinking, let alone biography and personality all combine to create his style. However, even though style is such a complex phenomenon, there is one area of creativity where style stands out at first glance. This is the language of the writer. The writer's skill, aesthetic principles, ability to notice the colors of life, and the ability to feel subtle differences are clearly visible in the language. Toghay Murad’s thoughts on artistic language and style are also worthy of attention. Since the artistic language and style is a mirror that expresses the soul, talent and originality of the creator, it is appropriate to study it in connection with the creator's worldview, language, literary-aesthetic ideal and artistic skills. Philosophical-aesthetic attitude of the writer to the events of life and the skill of creating a national character and using the tools of artistic representation, as well as the vitality and consistency of his thinking and observation, as well as the peculiarities of the author's biography - all together form his individual and unique style. and perfects.

We all know that Toghay Murad was a writer with his unique original style. Not only major critics and literary experts who have constantly followed the writer's work, but also every sensitive reader who is more or less aware of today's literary process, will appreciate his literary works, first of all, his unique colorful language reminiscent of prose poems, his poetic style. will find out without difficulty. This aspect of our famous writer distinguishes him from other artists.

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